

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE "TOURISM 4.0" CONCEPT IN TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077547>

Annotation. Modern in the world tourism many people of life indispensable to the part became smart tourism technologies of tourism stable development and touristic product quality to increase help giving different methods and of means combination is considered.

Keywords: Tourism 4.0, globalization, digital trends, traveller , tourist, IT-technology.

Uzbekistan his own many historical-architectural monuments , turf different climate and fast in paces development with whole the world attention to himself is pulling

Modern digital century is this as industry 4.0 named new of the period Beginning is a computer of the world from strength use through industry more more efficient to do desire own into takes. By Industry 4.0 present done new generation technologies whole the world across many to areas variable effect showed .

Tourism 4.0 tourists experience improve for advanced technologies and digital from solutions to use based on tourism development new era Version 4.0 tourism of the industry more modern , integrated and stable to be for evolution shows .

Tourism 4.0 main aspects one this to travelers customized services present reach for artificial intellect and big from the data is to use . The car learning algorithms and big data from the analysis used without companies each of the traveller desire and of interests come came out without visit commanding places , hotels, restaurants and another attention deserves places for customized recommendations offer to do.

Tourism 4.0 again one important aspect unique and immersive travel experience Create for virtual and extended for real is to use ancient ruins pilgrimage from doing pull , necklace on the rocks immersion , virtual reality to travelers physical there is without being of the world beauty and feel the diversity enable gives.

Smart tourism of technologies main structural from the parts one information systems and online of resources use is considered They are to tourists different attractions , routes , services and events about current and

reliable from the data use enable gives of this using tourists the most interesting and acceptable options Choose your travels efficient planning can of the world all in countries income bringer the most important from networks one was tourism digitization this to the process significant effect is showing . Mainly in tourism digital transformation tourism companies interested parties and to the market effect does and of tourists new generation profile creates.

Digital global boundaries in the world lost is going Digitization as a result people every one of his life at the stage of the internet and mobile from devices wide use started. Indeed , tourists going places there how what to go to do possibility , food and entertainment options from where find all digital applications through are learning . Based on this , they another of tourists stories and comments based on decision acceptance they do , then while belongs to on platforms own experiences with they share .

Tourism recreation of people and interesting time transfer , new experience gain for travel to do and that's it with national to the economy contribution to add for the work from his life time separate possible has been service show field as is defined . Therefore , the service show field with depends " tourism " country of activity a lot edged field it is economic , social , cultural and natural environment with constant in touch will be Also tourism _ activity developing countries and directions for income , employment and currency flow provides [7].

Technology a person of life indispensable element as of competition fast development , networks in the middle productivity increase is also available _ market business environment to improve help gives _ Tourism , transport and communication of technologies development people to relax / to relax was _ the need for tourism in the field of products / services diversity increases , tourists number growth while the world economy big liquidity flow provides . Therefore _ to digitization tooth _ tourism field for national to the economy adding contribution in terms of important [3].

Tourism in the field digital trends of tourists hopes is changing . Today's travel customers only they are for customized experience and solutions they want This point of view literally , digital to transformation has become travel the world personalized experiences , omnichannel customers experience , virtual reality , real -time marketing, message exchange platforms and chatbots such as from technologies use through business to the results positive effect show started _ , mobile integration , data based on approach and artificial intelligence [6].

In 2009, " smart tourism " World tourism organization by defined . in 2015 information and communication technologies this to the definition included . However, in 2017, " smart to tourism". today's the approach account received without , big data (BigData), objects internet and smart directions own into received definition given _ Tourism 4.0 information technologies and tourism in himself embodied and modern innovations with supported tourism activity as is defined . This attitude with Tourism 4.0 five of the element integration represents : tourism , government , natural area, calculation center and business _ Mainly , main the goal stability within competition conditions improve through tourism experience improve and satisfaction maximum level is to increase [5].

Today's in the day tourism field such as a lot fields new technologies using being changed to see can _ Tourists and tourism companies are also in the field changes and from changes serious effect is showing. Innovations and from changes informed has been people touristic activity with when engaged their needs and hopes satisfy will receive to businesses appeal they do This attitude with local and / or foreign tourists innovations with step by step be _ will receive tourism companies preferred they see Therefore , tourism _ enterprises digital to the century suitable respectively tourism in the field competitive superiority to provide strives _ Current at the time companies touristic activity with want to do has been of people expectations and needs satisfy for different strategies according to studies conduct need _ After all, digital transformation attention with watching to go and him business processes adaptation only through companies to competitors relatively efficiency to increase can _

Tourism digital transformation in the process work developed technologies tourists from coming before and after them makes it easier and themselves feel comfortable _ for wide opportunities offer does _ For example , smart cards using tourists hotel address , attention deserves places map and another many p things to see opportunity have _ In tourism blockchain technology without intermediaries the work real time environment mode tourism experience one instantly observation , demand and offer observation enable gives _ From this besides , it is tourism sector for faithfulness programs work output , customers comments online observation , limits and interested parties in the middle money safe transfer and loads observation such as many in the fields application can _ Artificial intellect and robotics technologies to the consumer effect who does sales , customers with connections and the like in processes applied to customers more to himself it feels special .

Today's in the day new customer (tourist), he is visiting to order decision did to the city upon arrival , the hotel technological in terms of equipped to be preferred sees _ The same at the moment " smart" . " hotels " appeared that 's it _ in tourism digital of transformation again one indicator . Smart hotels to the guests more customized amenities offer does _ This point of view meaning , tourists themselves is located hotel of the room light , temperature and from video systems from , many systems manage can _ So tourists _ _ their own in the rooms convenience control to do and all kind of digital from amenities enjoy to be can _ From this in addition to this systems only personal telephone through manage possible to the guests From covid next period more and more becoming popular the upcoming " contactless " holiday from experience enjoy to be enable gives _ From this except robots _ already some in hotels tourists waiting are getting National and / or international to business example in Japan _ robots by managed by the name "Henn na hotel". the hotel to bring can _ This is in the hotel all operations robots by done is increased [2]. Other giving examples _ transition Joiz : To the world of a robot named "Connie". famous Hilton hotels in the network service does _ So today _ _ in the day in hotels you robot house servants , robot waiters , robot cleaners and robot chefs you will find can _ hotel managers technology different to operations expendable time and labor shorten and service show quality improve they wait

Most of the time tourism almost always _ experience gain is a tool , but sometimes people by them happy who does and his life enriching to himself special activities as well as travel bloggers such as important income source as acceptance will be done . Digital in the century tourists own their travels planning , travel information study , booking to do and purchase in doing often the Internet and mobile from technologies they use This attitude with tourists themselves _ went places , taste saw food and drinks about impressions social in networks accounts and another on platforms share to see started _ Thus they are own _ to acquaintances visit ordered places about information they gave

Two main from the element , that is touristic demand and from the offer organize found tourism sector country economy in strengthening big role plays _ This point of view in terms of tourism regional and national to develop , in the past and in the future of countries economic growth and employment positive effect showing is a field . From this besides , tourism field invisible _ export as to the country currency flow provides capital _ the stakes increases and of income regions in the middle-distribution improves . Indeed , tourism sector purchase to do and trips organize reach , regional products sales , entertainment ,

accommodation , telecommunications , transport, food and drinks and the like services such as all services cover takes and national to the economy big contribution adds [1] .

In tourism digital transformation tourists number of tourism also positive for income effect to show is expected . This point of view in terms of technology and of communications development own on the contrary finds and smart tourism approaches appear will be Tourism 4.0 information , technology and innovations integration through in tourism additional _ value to create directed . 21st century development technologies and digital of the century Beginning whole the world across travel and tourism of the fields development take came _

Smart of technologies appear to be with not only business practices , perhaps many economy networks strategies are also serious is changing . Smart technologies with equipped enterprises travel experiences design and control to do can _ Smart of tourism development tourists recognize to get and to them suitable options present to do help gives _ Actually , smart tourism activity customers the need satisfy through competitive superiority provides and income increase through expenses reduces _ Indeed , in the world happen happening technological changes to the country visit commanding tourists number , tourism income and gross internal tourism in the product (GDP). of income share increase through economic development strengthen is expected . In the sector new technological of products to use possibility giver smart to tourism investments through created infrastructure stable to tourism contribution adds. Also for managers globally _ own from competitors forward transition and of tourists new generation profile organize doer service show consumers attraction to do for tourism companies strategy innovations quickly inputs needed [4].

Tourism field country economy contribution adds , population _ employment provides and currency income provides . Tourism is global digitization and digitization processes business processes changed from fields one is considered The same at the time smart within the framework of tourism (Tourism 4.0). information and communication technologies , cloud calculation , extended and virtual reality technologies , blockchain , artificial intelligence , robot systems , applications and services such as a lot new technologies there is of the device location and internal recommendations system according to Tourism in the field such smart technologies hotels , museums , cafes and in restaurants meeting can _ In practice that's it to see maybe traditional _ tourism digital tourism with replacement inevitable because " smart " transformation _

tourism from the beginning until the end changes . Today's in the day of a person trip home from your computer begins . People now online platforms and from applications new directions _ Search for flights reservation do , leave on time what that they do planning and even from vacation after evaluation for they use Smartphone applications , social networks , expanded and virtual reality and 360- degree video is traditional the trip to finish take came factors as travel to the industry significant effect showed . However , digitized tourism industry opportunities inequality , data safety and cyber security point of view in terms of some risks cause release can _

Summary by doing in other words , Tourism 4.0 travelers and tourism industry for new horizons opens . Personalized experiences , virtual reality , blockchain technologies and stability of these all of them customers good attraction make it safer operations and to the environment relatively responsible to practices help gives _ Tourism 4.0 is it his development resources learning and investment to enter worth it the future

Tourists today's new generation each of his travels stage is interactive . These are tourists their own big or bad experiences social networks through everyone with share to see can _ Therefore , digital _ transformation of tourists is also changing expectations and tourism industry this to the situation requires addition . _ This attitude with tourism companies digital transformation with step by step to be and accordingly _ respectively competitiveness to increase need _ Smart (digital) tourism for tourism enterprises to innovation investment inputs , technology for budget separation and they are to work will receive worker to the power belongs to qualifications provide for necessary training their provision need

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